

ANALYTIC DESCRIPTIONS OF 3-D PREFORMS USED IN COMPOSITE COMPONENT MANUFACTURING

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SUMMARY: In order to quantify the macro-mechanical response of composite materials-based engineering components, the physical micro-relationships of a unit cell yarn configuration is assumed to be repeated is considered important. The geometric undulations of the yarns that constitute the structure of a unit-cell is the focus of the analysis in this paper. The unit-cell's geometric description is idealised and is assumed to reliably represented by standard geometric lines. The unit-cell described here, consisted of six warp layers, seven weft layers and a binder yarn in the weft direction. This is only one of the several weave architectures designed and manufactured as part of the research program. The benefits of the analyses include the corroboration of the geometric model with computer-simulations of the unit cell geometry and predictive models of physical entities such as volume fractions and yarn tensions. Analytic relationships of yarn tensions with unit-cell-based geometric characteristics have been developed to corroborate physical observations. Analytic models of other geometric characteristics such as unit-cell binder length, weft and warp pitch have also all been compared with pictorial representations of the corresponding geometric feature.

KEYWORDS: Micro-features, Undulations, Weft and Warp Yarns, Architectures, Binder Length, Unit-cell, Predictive Models, Analytic Corroboration

INTRODUCTION

The macromechanical behaviour of polymer-matrix composite structures is partially dependent on the micro-geometric features of the yarn architectures. This paper uses the geometric details of a unit cell to describe some of the features that could be correlated to macromechanical performance. The computer modelling of these features and other related work have been reported in [1], [2], [3], [4]. Vital analytically useful data, such as volume fraction of fibres and tow misalignment, can be extracted from these computer models and compared to the geometric models given here.

Preform Geometrical Description

Work by Coman in [1] demonstrates that during the manufacturing process the preform architecture changes substantially. A geometrical description seems to be imposed for a better explanation of the structural and process parameter effects upon the final preform architecture.

An idealised preform architecture is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Schematic of idealised orthogonal weave architecture. Section X1

In principle most of the geometrical elements can be measured and some of them are calculated based on mathematical relations established between them. The geometrical features used to define the architectural parameters are described in the following subsections.

Separation Space

The separation space represents the distance between the projections of two yarn centres (warp, weft, binder, warp-weft, etc.). A yarn centre is considered to be the centroid point.

a. If the yarn projection is made on vertical axis, O-Z, the following symbols are chosen: S_{wiwj} , S_{fifj} , S_{bibj} , S_{wifj} , S_{wibj} , S_{fibj} . The two indices added to the symbol suggest which of the yarns were considered when the measurement was made. For example, the S_{w1f1} is the distance between the first warp (w_1) and first weft (f_1) measured on vertical axis; S_{wibj} is the distance between the warp i (w_i) and binder j (b_j).

As these separation spaces are measured on the vertical axis, they can be used to determine the thickness of the preform. The thickness can be expressed in few ways by summarising these spaces. Two alternatives are proposed in Equations (1) and (2).

The thickness can be determined by summarising the warp separation spaces:

$$t = S_{b1 w1} + S_{wnbk} + \sum_{i=1}^{i=n-1} S_{wi wi+1} \quad (1)$$

where n is the number of warp layers, and k is the number of binders. Note that the number of weft layers, in all the present structures, is equal to the number of warp layers minus one ($n-1$).

The thickness can also be expressed based on weft separation space like in the following equation:

$$t = S_{b1f1} + S_{fn-1bk} + \sum_{j=1}^{j=n-2} S_{fj fj+1} \quad (2)$$

An ideal structure incorporates the warps, wefts, and binders at equal intervals. However, during composite manufacturing, modifications of these separation spaces occurs. Consequently the separation space can express the measure of a tow misalignment or deflection from the ideal position.

b. If the warp centroids are projected on the horizontal axis, O-X, the space that separates two warp columns represents the warp pitch length (λ_w) or the warp geometrical density [mm]. The warp pitch length is determined by the reed number. For an ideal structure, all these lengths are equal. For ordinary cases, an average length has to be considered.

c. If the weft centroids are projected on the axis O-Y, the space that separates two consecutive weft columns is called weft pitch length (λ_t) or weft geometrical density [mm]. In the ideal situation, when all weft centroids are perfectly aligned, there is a

unique pitch length of the weft yarns, otherwise an average of the weft pitch has to be considered. The take-up, let-off motions and the beating force during the weaving process dictate the weft pitch length. If the length of warp released by let-off motion is equal to the length of weave rolled (by take-up motion) and the beating force is constant, then all the wefts are perfectly aligned one on top of each other. Hence, all the wefts' centroids are perfectly aligned.

Undulation Degree

The undulation degree defines the deviation of a yarn axis from the straight (ideal) position. Undulation degree has been defined in two ways using its components:

Undulation amplitude (h)

Referring to an undulated yarn, Lord P.R. and Mohamed M.H., [3] outlined the *amplitude* as “a term which defines the maximum excursion of an oscillating body from its mean position”.

Measured only for crimped yarns, the undulation amplitude represents the projection on the vertical axis of the higher extreme and lower extreme yarn position. As shown in Figure 1, for the case of a binder (which is the case of an undulated yarn) two distinct parts can be defined: straight and crimped. If these parts are projected on the vertical axis and summarised, this yields the undulation amplitude.

For the present work all the crimped yarns were considered to have a sinusoidal path.

$$\mathbf{h} = (\mathbf{h}_{\text{str}} + \mathbf{h}_{\text{cr}}) / 2 \quad (3)$$

\mathbf{h}_{str} = the amplitude of straight part

\mathbf{h}_{cr} = the amplitude of crimped part

Undulation angle (α).

The undulation angle was measured for all three yarn types, warp, weft, binder and have the symbol α_b , α_w , α_f . They represent the deviation angles measured between binder, warp, or weft middle axis and X or Y axis. In other words, the undulation angle is a measure of yarn waviness or crimping. The expected effect of any tow waviness is that it reduces axial stiffness. An attempt to correlate the binder undulation angle with reed density (warp pitch length) and thickness was carried out as shown in the next paragraph.

Consider the plane X-Z on which only the warp cross-section and the binder profile can be viewed. A quarter of an idealised Unit Cell is considered (see Unit Cell symmetry Figure 2).

Figure 2. The geometry of a quarter of a Unit Cell

Remark: The binder is always tangential to the warp cross-sectional contour.

If this is so, consider the binder tangent to the top warp cross-sectional boundary, and the tangency point **T**. The tangency point coordinates, in the plane Z-X, are (x_t, z_t) .

Because x_t is in fact $(\lambda_w/2 - b_1/2)$ and z_t is $t/2 - a_1/2$ the tangency point can be represented as

$$\mathbf{T} [(\lambda_w/2 - b_1/2), t/2 - a_1/2]. \quad (4)$$

Consider also that the warp shape is a lent that can be constructed by joining two parabolas $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ that have the expression:

$$z = f_1(x) = Ax^2 + Bx + C \quad (5)$$

Also the binder was considered to be a line tangent to the parabolas $f_1(x)$ in the point **T**.

Following are the three mathematical criteria (numbered C1, C2, C3) that have to be satisfied when considering a parabola and a tangent line as in the Figure 2:

$$\text{C1. } f_1(\lambda_w/2 - b_1/2) = t/2 - a_1/2 \Rightarrow f_1[(\lambda_w - b_1)/2] = (t - a_1)/2 \quad (6)$$

$$\text{C2. } f_1(\lambda_w/2 + b_1/2) = t/2 - a_1/2 \Rightarrow f_1[(\lambda_w + b_1)/2] = (t - a_1)/2 \quad (7)$$

$$\text{C3. } f_1'(\lambda_w/2 - b_1/2) = \tan \alpha \quad (8)$$

$f_1(x)$ was considered to have the expression as in Equation (5), the derivative

$f_1'(x) = 2Ax + B$. Then Equation (8) becomes:

$$\text{c3. } 2A(\lambda_w/2 - b_1/2) + B = \tan \alpha \quad (9)$$

The first and second criteria demonstrates that the values of the function $f_1(x)$ at its extremities are identical.

The third criteria demonstrates that the derivative function $f_1'(x)$ in a tangency point is equal to the tangent of the angle made by parabola and line [5].

But, $A = t/2 - a_1/2$, $B = \lambda_w/2$, and $C = t/2$

If these terms are replaced in Equation (5-8) it results;

$$2(t/2 - a_1/2)(\lambda_w/2 - b_1/2) + \lambda_w/2 = \tan \alpha \quad (10)$$

$$\tan \alpha = (t - a_1)(\lambda_w - b_1) + \lambda_w \quad (11)$$

or, the interlacing angle is dependent on warp pitch length and thickness. When the warp tow dimensions and the reed number are known, it is easy to determine the binder interlacing angle.

Threads Length Within The Unit Cell: l_w , l_f , l_b

As was previously mentioned there are two reasons that gives importance to the thread length as parameter. The first reason is that the tow length helps to determine the fibre volume fraction; the second one is that it gives information about the crimping level within the composite.

There are two cases that have to be discussed- crimped and uncrimped yarns. These are described below:

The case of a crimped yarn.

To exemplify the case of a crimped yarn, a binder was selected (due to the fact that by architecture the binder is the most crimped yarn within the unit cell).

As can be seen in Figure 1, the binder or the crimped yarn, is made out of straight segments and crimped segments. To ease the binder length calculation the crimped part

of the tow was considered to be an arc circle, defined by the h_{cr} . By summarising the crimped and straight segments the tow length within the unit cell is determined.

According to Figure 1. only half of the path length is considered due to the fact the structure is symmetric to Z-Y axis. Thus, to calculate the entire length, all the segments were multiplied by 2. In the following equations, all the crimped segments are:

$$l_{crimped} = l_{binder} = 2[AB + \widehat{BC} + CD + DE + \widehat{EF} + FG] = 2[AB + \widehat{BC} + CE + \widehat{EF} + FG]$$

$$2[x + h_{cr}/2 * \pi/2 + h_{str}/\sin\alpha + h_{cr}/2 * \pi/2 + x] = 2[2x + h_{cr} * \pi/2 + h_{str}/\sin\alpha] \quad (12)$$

But according to the geometrical description, Figure 1, the following relation is also satisfied:

$$\lambda_w = 2x + h_{cr} + m = 2x + h_{cr} + \cos\alpha CE = 2x + h_{cr} + \cos\alpha h_{str}/\sin\alpha, \text{ or written differently}$$

$$2x = \lambda_w - h_{cr} - \cos\alpha h_{str}/\sin\alpha \quad (13)$$

If in Equation (12) the term $2x$ is replaced with its expression (Equation (13)), it results:

$$l_{binder} = 2[\lambda_w - h_{cr} - \cos\alpha h_{str}/\sin\alpha + h_{cr} * \pi/2 + h_{str}/\sin\alpha], \text{ or is equal to}$$

$$l_{binder} = 2[\lambda_w + h_{cr}(\pi/2 - 1) + h_{str}/\sin\alpha (1 - \cos\alpha)] \quad (14)$$

The main objective of the preform conception was to produce a structure that has uncrimped warps and wefts and a binder that penetrates through the composite at an angle of 90^0 . In relation to the binder penetration angle, it was shown (via weaving experiments) that two main situations can occur:

1) An ideal situation in which $\alpha = 90^0$ and thus $\sin 90^0=1$ and $\cos 90^0 = 0$. Equation (14) becomes:

$$l_{binder} = 2[\lambda_w + h_{cr}(\pi/2 - 1) + h_{str}] = 2\lambda_w + 2h_{cr}(\pi/2 - 1) + 2h_{str} = 2\lambda_w + h_{cr} + 2h_{str} \quad (15)$$

$$l_{binder} \text{ max} = 2\lambda_w + 2t - h_{cr} \quad (16)$$

Equation (16) includes terms that are easier to be determined. In most of the cases, h_{cr} was found to be equal to the separation space of the top two warp layers.

2) A situation limit when the binder does not penetrate through the preform at 90^0 angle. For this particular situation, it was observed a length limit under which the structure exhibited great crimping.

When the binder penetration angle (interlacing angle) $\alpha = 45^\circ$, $\sin 45^\circ = \cos 45^\circ = 0.707$, the binder length was designated to have a minimum length and Equation (15) becomes:

$$l_{\text{binder min}} = 2[\lambda_w + h_{\text{cr}}(\pi/2 - 1) + h_{\text{str}}/0.707(1 - 0.707)] \cong 2\lambda_w + t$$

$$l_{\text{binder min}} \cong 2\lambda_w + t \quad (17)$$

In order to achieve a perfect architecture, it is likely to design a binder that has the length close to the superior limit ($l_{\text{binder max}}$).

In between the superior limit and the minimum limit, the architecture could remain undistorted (if the warp and weft tensions are correlated)

If the binder is designed to have a value under the minimum limit ($l_{\text{binder min}}$) great warps and wefts misalignment can occur within the preform.

If binder penetration angle is close to 90° the straight part of the yarn is higher and the crimped part is smaller .

In the case of a noncrimped yarn, the length is considered to be the Unit Cell length or width. The wefts will have the UC width value and the warps will have the UC length value. All composite materials' properties are strongly dependent on the fibrous microstructure, fibre volume fraction and the packing arrangement of the fibres.

While the tow's microstructural elements (i.e. fibre diameter) are unchangeable during the composite formation process, the tow fibre volume fraction and packing arrangement, the fibre position within the tow is considerably altered.

Fibre Volume Fraction Calculation

A fibre volume fraction expression based on Unit Cell components volume is proposed. The warp, weft and binder volumes are determined individually and thereafter are summarised.

Warp volume:

$$V_w = N_{wc} * L_w * l_w * T_{\text{tex}_w} * 10^{-6} / \delta \quad [\text{mm}^3] \quad (18)$$

Weft volume:

$$V_f = N_{fc} * L_F * l_f * T_{\text{tex}_f} * 10^{-6} / \delta \quad [\text{mm}^3] \quad (19)$$

Binder volume:

$$V_b = N_{bc} * L_B * l_{\text{binder}} * T_{\text{tex}_b} * 10^{-6} / \delta \quad [\text{mm}^3] \quad (20)$$

$$V_b = N_{bc} * L_B * 2[\lambda_w + h_{cr}(\pi/2 - 1) + h_{str}/\sin\alpha (1 - \cos\alpha)] * T_{tex} * 10^{-6} / \delta \text{ [mm}^3\text{]} \quad (21)$$

where δ is the fibre density measured in g/cm^3

N_{wc} , N_{fc} , N_{bc} is the number of the warp, weft and binder columns within the UC.

L_w , L_f , L_b is the number of warp, weft and binder layers within a column;

l_w , l_f , l_b is the length of the warp, weft, binder within a unit cell;

T_{tex_w} , T_{tex_f} , T_{tex_b} is the linear density of the warp, weft and binder tow and is expressed in [g/1000 meters]

In Equation (21) the binder length was considered to have the expression of Equation (14). Depending on the binder interlacing angle the binder volume can use the expression of binder length (l_{binder}) from Equation (16) or (17).

The Equations (18) and (19) offer the opportunity to adapt the expression of l_w and l_f to the case of crimped or uncrimped yarn, depending on the structure examined.

The composite volume is actually the UC's volume and is equal to:

$$V_c = L \ w \ t \quad \text{[mm}^3\text{]} \quad (22)$$

Where L is the UC length, w is the UC width and t is its thickness

Conclusions

In this paper, a geometrical description of the preform was made and its parameters were defined to be: separation space, undulation degree, and thread or yarn length. Some equations for the limit of the binder length under which the preform exhibits crimping were developed. The fibre volume fraction was related with the composite components through the Equations (18) to (22). These geometric models were compared favourably with the data extraction features of the computer models details of which been reported elsewhere [1], [2].

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